

Monte Carlo Estimation of Software Reliability for Component Size, Stopping Time, and
Probability Sensitivity

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A Thesis Submitted in Partial
Fulfillment of the Requirements
for the Degree of
Master of Science
in the field of Mathematics

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May, 2026

ABSTRACT

MONTE CARLO ESTIMATION OF SOFTWARE RELIABILITY FOR COMPONENT SIZE, STOPPING TIME, AND PROBABILITY SENSITIVITY

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Monte Carlo methods are used to estimate the reliability of a series system with $m = 3$ components under an imperfect debugging framework. Two key probabilities are introduced: p_j , the probability of successfully removing a bug from component j , and q_j , the probability of introducing a new bug during the bug removal process. System reliability is estimated using component-level failure counts through a counting process and a maximum likelihood approach. The simulation study identifies the appropriate component size s and optimal stopping time τ^* that lead to stable and accurate reliability estimates, using a relative change threshold as the stopping criterion. A sensitivity analysis shows that increasing p_j or decreasing q_j consistently improves system reliability, while reversing these effects reduces reliability. These findings provide practical guidance for managing the debugging process in multi-component series systems.

Keywords: Counting process, Imperfect debugging, Maximum likelihood estimation, Sensitivity analysis, Series system, System reliability

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

First, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my advisor, Dr. Marcus A. Agustin, for his guidance and support throughout this work. His advice and encouragement helped me a lot during the difficult times of this research. I would also like to thank my committee members for their helpful comments and suggestions, which improved this work significantly. Lastly, I am deeply thankful to my family for their love and support. Without their encouragement and patience, completing this work would not have been possible.

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CHAPTER 1

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE RELIABILITY

Software systems are now a very important part of everyday life, and they are used in almost every area, from banking and healthcare to transportation and communication. Because of this, making sure that a software is reliable has become one of the most important goals in software engineering. Software reliability is defined as the probability that a software system runs without failure for a given period of time under certain conditions. Over the years, many researchers have worked on building mathematical models to describe how software failures happen and how the debugging process affects the overall reliability of a system.

One of the earliest and most well-known models in this area was proposed by Jelinski and Moranda [JM72]. Their model assumed that the software starts with a fixed number of bugs N , that each bug contributes equally to the failure rate, and that once a bug is found, it is immediately and perfectly removed. The hazard function of the Jelinski-Moranda model is given by

$$\lambda_i(t; N, \phi) = (N - (i - 1))\phi, \quad t_{i-1} < t \leq t_i,$$

where N is the initial number of bugs, ϕ is the constant failure rate contribution of each individual bug, and i is the index of the current failure interval. This model gave researchers a useful starting point, but its assumption of perfect debugging and constant failure rates turned out to be a major limitation. Goel and Okumoto [GO79] later proposed a non-homogeneous Poisson process model where the error detection rate changes over time, which made the model more flexible and more realistic. In their model, the mean value function of the cumulative number of failures is given by

$$m(t) = a (1 - e^{-bt})$$

where a represents the expected total number of failures and b is the fault detection rate. The corresponding failure intensity takes the form

$$\lambda(t) = abe^{-bt},$$

which shows that the failure rate decreases over time as more bugs are detected and removed, reflecting an exponential reliability growth pattern. Around the same time, Ohba [Ohb84] introduced reliability growth models that follow an S-shaped curve, where errors are detected slowly at the beginning of the testing, then faster as testing progresses, and then slowing down again as fewer bugs remain. Yamada, Ohba and Osaki [YOO83] also developed S-shaped reliability growth models and proposed a mean value function of the form

$$m(t) = a (1 - (1 + bt)e^{-bt})$$

with the corresponding failure intensity

$$\lambda(t) = ab^2te^{-bt},$$

which has been widely used in the software reliability literature because it captures the initial learning phase of testing more naturally than the exponential model. Goel [Goe85] then provided a broad review of the assumptions, limitations, and applicability of these early models, pointing out several ways in which they did not fully reflect what happens in real software development.

One of the most important limitations that came out of this review was the assumption that every detected bug is always successfully removed with probability one. In practice, this

is often not the case. Developers do not always fully fix the fault they are working on, and sometimes the changes they make to fix one bug end up creating a new bug somewhere else in the system. This is what is known as imperfect debugging, and it has received a lot of attention in recent research. Mahapatra and Roy [MR12] modified the Jelinski-Moranda model to include imperfect debugging and showed that relaxing the perfect removal assumption leads to quite different reliability estimates compared to the original model. Huang, Chiu and Chen [HCC22] also developed a software reliability growth model that takes imperfect debugging into account by considering both the probability of successfully removing a bug and the probability of introducing a new one during the debugging process. These contributions show that software reliability models need to reflect the real conditions of debugging in order to give useful results.

With this in mind, the present study considers a system reliability model for a series system of m components, where the failure of any single component causes the entire system to fail. Following the work of Agustin, Agustin and Thompson [AAT21], we use the counting process framework to model the failure and debugging process of each component. In contrast to Agustin [Agu99], who assumed that bugs are always removed with certainty, this model introduces two important probabilities: p_j , which is the probability that a bug is successfully removed, and q_j , which is the probability that a new bug is introduced while removing a bug.

Since the modified model involves unknown parameters, estimation is an important part of this study. The maximum likelihood estimators of the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\beta, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_m, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)$ are derived and their large sample properties are established. Following Agustin, Agustin and Thompson [AAT21], the system reliability estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ is obtained using the invariance property of the maximum likelihood estimator, and its asymptotic properties are used throughout the analysis.

To support the theoretical results and to evaluate the performance of the estimators under different settings, a Monte Carlo simulation study is carried out in this thesis. Monte Carlo

methods are a broad class of computational techniques that use repeated random sampling to obtain numerical results and to approximate quantities that are difficult or impossible to compute analytically. The idea behind Monte Carlo simulation was formally introduced by Metropolis and Ulam [MU49], and since then it has grown into one of the most widely used tools in statistics, engineering, and many other fields. The general framework and theory of Monte Carlo methods are covered in detail by Robert and Casella [RC04] and Fishman [Fis96], both of which provide comprehensive treatments of how these methods work and how they can be applied in statistical contexts. In reliability engineering specifically, Goldfeld and Dubi [GD87] were among the early contributors who demonstrated how Monte Carlo methods can be used to evaluate and assess system reliability, while Glasserman [Gla03] and, Chen and Jeff Hong [CJH07] have shown how these methods can be applied effectively in more complex engineering and financial settings.

In the context of this study, Monte Carlo simulation is used for two main purposes. The first is to determine the appropriate component size s , which is the system size needed for the asymptotic properties of the estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ to hold reasonably well in practice. Since the theoretical results are derived under large sample assumptions, the simulation study helps identify how large s needs to be in order for the estimator to behave well. The second purpose is to find the optimal stopping time, which is the point during the testing process at which it is no longer beneficial to continue debugging. Together, these two goals make the simulation study a central part of this thesis, as they bridge the gap between the theoretical framework and its practical application.

An important practical question in software reliability is knowing when to stop testing. Stopping too early means that many bugs may still be present in the system, while stopping too late increases testing costs without much gain in reliability. Several researchers have studied this problem from different angles. Dalal and Mallows [DM90] developed graphical tools to help decide when to stop testing based on a cost-reliability tradeoff. Singpurwalla

[Sin91] approached the problem using a decision theory approach, proposing an optimal testing interval based on maximizing expected utility. Yang and Chao [YC95] compared several stopping rules and showed that a common and practical approach is to stop testing when the reliability has reached a certain threshold. More recently, Agustin, Agustin and DeRousse[AAD23] developed a stopping procedure specifically for systems that assume imperfect removal of defects, which is directly related to the framework used in this study. In this paper, we use a relative change threshold as the stopping criterion, where testing is stopped when the change in the estimated system reliability $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ between successive debugging stages falls below a prespecified small value. This criterion is practical and easy to implement, and it ensures that testing continues only as long as meaningful improvements in reliability are still being achieved.

In addition to finding the appropriate component size and the optimal stopping time, this study also investigates how changes in the debugging probabilities p_j and q_j affect the estimated system reliability. Understanding this relationship is useful because it gives insight into how the quality of the debugging process, in terms of how well bugs are removed and how often new ones are introduced, influences the overall reliability of the system. This kind of sensitivity analysis helps software managers and developers make better decisions about when to stop testing and how much effort to invest in improving the debugging process.

The rest of this thesis is organized as follows. Chapter 2 presents the model while describing the estimation procedure and the asymptotic properties of the estimators. Chapter 3 presents the simulation study and the results, and Chapter 4 concludes the paper with a summary and directions for future work.

CHAPTER 2

SIMULATION-BASED RELIABILITY MODELING FRAMEWORK

We examine a series system that consists of m components, where if any one component fails, the entire system fails as well. To keep things simple and easy to follow, this paper focuses on a three-component series system, although the results can be extended to any number of components without much difficulty. Here, T_j denotes the failure time of component j , for $j = 1, 2, 3$, and the overall system failure time is defined as,

$$T = \min(T_1, T_2, T_3).$$

When a system fails, the component that caused the failure is identified and debugged. However, not all system failures are considered in this model. Some failures occur because of outside reasons, for example, a sudden power cut or a hardware problem, and these are not what we are focusing on. We only look at failures that happen because of bugs inside the system components, where the responsible component is identified, and a debugging process is carried out to remove the bug. This paper takes a more realistic approach by considering that debugging is not always perfect and successful. We introduce the probability p_j , which represents the probability that a bug is successfully removed and q_j which is the probability that a new bug is introduced to the system while removing a bug. By including both p_j and q_j , the new model becomes more realistic and better represents the situations that actually occur during real-world software debugging and maintenance. The probabilities p_j and q_j for $j = 1, 2, 3$ are fixed and satisfy the following two conditions.

1. Both p_j and q_j satisfy $0 \leq p_j \leq 1$ and $0 \leq q_j \leq 1$.
2. p_j must always be greater than q_j .

The second condition is more important in this study. If this condition was reversed, i.e. if $q_j > p_j$, the residual number of bugs in the system would keep increasing over time, because new bugs are being introduced faster than existing ones are removed. This means that the residual number of bugs would never decrease, and as a result, the system would never improve in terms of reliability, making the debugging process meaningless. So, to keep the system in a state where debugging is still useful and the residual number of bugs is actually decreasing over time, the probability of successfully removing a bug must always be higher than the probability of introducing a new one.

We use the counting process framework, as described by Agustin, Agustin and Thompson [AAT21], to track and identify the number of bugs that cause system failures. Based on this framework, the hazard function is given by

$$\lambda_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{cases} \beta, & j = 0, \\ \gamma_j (B_j - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)), & j = 1, \dots, m, \end{cases} \quad (2.1)$$

where the parameter vector of interest is $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\beta, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_m, B_1, \dots, B_m)$. The parameter β corresponds to the hazard rate for outside failures, such as power cuts or other external factors that are not related to software bugs. Since these outside failures are not caused by any system component, they are not the focus of this study, and we do not investigate them further. Once a failure due to component j is observed, the hazard function for each component j depends on γ_j , the failure rate contribution of a bug, and B_j , which represents the initial number of bugs in component j . The term $(p_j - q_j)$ captures the net effect of the debugging process, and $N_j(t-)$ tracks the cumulative number of component j failures observed just before time t . Together, these quantities allow the hazard function to update dynamically over time as failures occur and debugging takes place.

Using the counting process framework, the likelihood function is obtained by assuming a

fixed testing period $[0, \tau]$ and is given by,

$$L_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \prod_{j=0}^m \exp \left(\int_0^\tau \log \lambda_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}) dN_j(t) - \int_0^\tau \lambda_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}) dt \right). \quad (2.2)$$

The log-likelihood is then obtained by taking the natural logarithm of $L_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ in (2.2) to get

$$\ell_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \sum_{j=0}^m \left(\int_0^\tau \log \lambda_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}) dN_j(t) - \int_0^\tau \lambda_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}) dt \right). \quad (2.3)$$

To get the maximum likelihood estimates, we maximize $\ell_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ given in (2.3) with respect to the parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$. The score equations are obtained by taking the partial derivatives of the log-likelihood with respect to $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ that is,

$$U_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{\partial \ell_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\theta}}. \quad (2.4)$$

For $j = 0$, the score equation for β is

$$\frac{\partial \ell_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \beta} = \int_0^\tau \frac{1}{\beta} dN_0(t) - \tau = 0, \quad (2.5)$$

and for $j = 1, \dots, m$, the score equations for γ_j and B_j are, respectively,

$$\frac{\partial \ell_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial \gamma_j} = \int_0^\tau \frac{1}{\gamma_j} dN_j(t) - \int_0^\tau (B_j - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)) dt = 0, \quad (2.6)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta})}{\partial B_j} = \int_0^\tau \frac{1}{B_j - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)} dN_j(t) - \int_0^\tau \gamma_j dt = 0. \quad (2.7)$$

The maximum likelihood estimators are obtained by solving the likelihood equations with respect to the parameters of interest as follows,

Derivation of $\hat{\beta}_\tau$: Starting with (2.5) the score equation for β , β can be pulled out of the

integral since it is a constant with respect to t , giving

$$\frac{1}{\beta} \int_0^\tau dN_0(t) = \tau.$$

Noting that $\int_0^\tau dN_0(t) = N_0(\tau)$, we have

$$\frac{N_0(\tau)}{\beta} = \tau,$$

and solving directly for β yields

$$\hat{\beta}_\tau = \frac{N_0(\tau)}{\tau}.$$

Derivation of $\hat{\gamma}_{j\tau}$: Starting with (2.6) the score equation for γ_j , we get

$$\frac{1}{\gamma_j} \int_0^\tau dN_j(t) = \int_0^\tau (B_j - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)) dt.$$

Noting that $\int_0^\tau dN_j(t) = N_j(\tau)$, we have

$$\frac{N_j(\tau)}{\gamma_j} = \int_0^\tau (B_j - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)) dt,$$

and solving directly for γ_j yields

$$\hat{\gamma}_{j\tau} = \frac{N_j(\tau)}{\int_0^\tau (\hat{B}_{j\tau} - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)) dt},$$

where $\hat{\gamma}_j$ denotes the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) of the failure rate contribution of component j .

Derivation of $\hat{B}_{j\tau}$: Here, $\hat{B}_{j\tau}$ denotes the maximum likelihood estimator of the initial

number of bugs in component j . Starting with (2.7) the score equation for B_j , we have

$$\int_0^\tau \frac{1}{B_j - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)} dN_j(t) - \int_0^\tau \gamma_j dt = 0.$$

$$\int_0^\tau \frac{1}{B_j - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)} dN_j(t) - \gamma_j \tau = 0.$$

Substituting the MLE $\hat{\gamma}_{j\tau}$ into the right-hand side yields the expression for $\hat{B}_{j\tau}$ given by

$$\int_0^\tau \frac{1}{\hat{B}_{j\tau} - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-)} dN_j(t) - \frac{N_j(\tau)}{\int_0^\tau \left(\hat{B}_{j\tau} - (p_j - q_j)N_j(t-) \right) dt} \cdot \tau = 0.$$

It can be noticed that the estimators $\hat{\gamma}_{j\tau}$ and $\hat{B}_{j\tau}$ depend on each other, so they do not have a simple closed-form solution and need to be solved simultaneously. In practice, this is done by substituting one estimator into the other and solving the resulting equation numerically.

We introduce a reparameterization to study the large sample properties of the model following Agustin, Agustin and Thompson [AAT21]. Specifically, we let

$$B_j^{(n)} = s^{(n)} \alpha_j,$$

where $s^{(n)}$ is the size of a component and α_j represents the initial bug density per unit size of component j . The key asymptotic assumption here is that $s^{(n)} \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, meaning the component size grows large. In addition, we let the parameter for the outside failures of the n^{th} model to be $\beta^{(n)} = s^{(n)} \beta$.

Substituting $B_j^{(n)} = s^{(n)} \beta$ and $\beta^{(n)}$ into the hazard function given in equation (2.1), the modified hazard function for the n^{th} model becomes

$$\lambda^{(n)}(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \begin{cases} s^{(n)}\beta, & j = 0, \\ s^{(n)}\gamma_j \left(\alpha_j - (p_j - q_j) \frac{N_j^{(n)}(t-)}{s^{(n)}} \right), & j = 1, \dots, m, \end{cases} \quad (2.8)$$

It can be seen that the component size $s^{(n)}$ now appears as a scaling factor in both cases of the hazard function. For $j = 0$, the baseline hazard is simply scaled by $s^{(n)}$. For $j = 1, \dots, m$, the term $\frac{N_j^{(n)}(t-)}{s^{(n)}}$ can be interpreted as the proportion of failures relative to the component size. With this reparameterization, the new parameter vector of interest becomes $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\beta, \gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_m, \alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_m)$. This parameterization is more suitable for the large sample setting, since $s^{(n)}$ is not a parameter to be estimated but rather a known quantity that grows large as $n \rightarrow \infty$. The large sample properties of the estimators are then used to determine an appropriate component size $s^{(n)}$ that ensures the estimators perform well and produce stable and reliable results, as will be discussed in the simulation study presented in the following sections. For the remainder of this thesis, we will suppress the dependence on n for ease of notation.

From Agustin, Agustin and Thompson [AAT21], we can make use of the asymptotic properties of $\frac{\mathbf{N}_j(t)}{s}$, where $\mathbf{N}(t) = (N_0(t), N_1(t), \dots, N_m(t))$. Particularly,

$$\frac{\mathbf{N}(t)}{s} \xrightarrow{pr} \mathbf{X}(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0) \quad (2.9)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\theta}^0 = (\beta^0, \gamma^0, \alpha^0)$ is the true value of the parameter vector, and the expected number of failures per unit size in component j up to time t is represented by $\mathbf{X}(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0) = (X_0(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0), X_1(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0), \dots, X_m(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0))$, evaluated at the true parameter values. More specifically, $X_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0)$ for each component j is defined as

$$X_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0) = \begin{cases} \beta^0 t, & j = 0 \\ \int_0^t \alpha_j^0 \gamma_j^0 e^{-\gamma_j^0 \int_0^u (p_j - q_j) dv} du, & j = 1, \dots, m \end{cases} \quad (2.10)$$

For $j = 0$, $X_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0)$ takes a simple linear form in t , reflecting a baseline failure process governed by β^0 . For components $j = 1, \dots, m$, α_j^0 and γ_j^0 are the true parameter values for component j , and the exponential term $e^{-\gamma_j^0 \int_0^u (p_j - q_j) dv}$ captures the cumulative effect of p_j and q_j on the failure intensity up to time u , where both satisfy $0 \leq q_j < p_j \leq 1$, ensuring that $p_j - q_j$ is strictly positive.

Evaluating the integral in equation (2.10) explicitly yields,

$$X_j(t; \boldsymbol{\theta}^0) = \begin{cases} \beta^0 t, & j = 0 \\ \frac{\alpha_j^0}{p_j - q_j} \left[1 - e^{-\gamma_j^0 (p_j - q_j) t} \right], & j = 1, \dots, m \end{cases} \quad (2.11)$$

This result allows us to substitute the random quantity $\frac{N_j(t)}{s}$ with $X_j(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}^0)$ when the component size s is sufficiently large, which greatly simplifies the subsequent analysis.

Taking advantage of this, the corresponding terms in the modified hazard function given in equation (2.8) were replaced by $X_j(t, \boldsymbol{\theta}^0)$, which simplifies the expressions and makes them easier to work with. Following this replacement, a Monte Carlo simulation study was carried out to find the appropriate component size s and to determine the optimal stopping time τ for the debugging process. The idea behind this simulation is to generate many replications under different settings and observe how the estimators behave, which provides a practical way to evaluate the performance of the model under realistic conditions.

The system reliability at time τ is given by

$$\rho_\tau(\boldsymbol{\theta}^0) = \frac{\beta^0}{\beta^0 + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma_j^0 \left(\alpha_j^0 - (p_j - q_j) \frac{N_j(\tau)}{s} \right)} \quad (2.12)$$

This expression was obtained by modifying the system reliability formula originally proposed by Agustin, Agustin and Thompson [AAT21] to reflect the structure of the updated model. It represents the probability that the system does not fail up to time τ . Since the true parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}^0$ is unknown in practice, computing ρ_τ from equation (2.12) directly is impossible. We apply the invariance property of the maximum likelihood estimator to obtain the estimator of the system reliability given by

$$\hat{\rho}_\tau = \frac{\hat{\beta}}{\hat{\beta} + \sum_{j=1}^m \hat{\gamma}_j \left(\hat{\alpha}_j - (p_j - q_j) \frac{N_j(\tau)}{s} \right)} \quad (2.13)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$ is the MLE of $\boldsymbol{\theta}^0$ obtained from the observed failure data. This estimator serves as a practical tool for assessing the reliability of the system at any given time τ .

We also make use of the asymptotic properties of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$. Specifically,

$$\hat{\rho}_\tau \xrightarrow{pr} \rho_\tau^0 = \frac{\beta^0}{\beta^0 + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma_j^0 \alpha_j^0 e^{-\gamma_j^0 (p_j - q_j) \tau}} \quad (2.14)$$

and

$$\sqrt{s} (\hat{\rho}_\tau - \rho_\tau^0) \xrightarrow{d} N(0, \sigma^2) \quad (2.15)$$

where σ^2 is the asymptotic variance of the estimator.

It is important to note that these asymptotic results were originally established by Agustin, Agustin and Thompson [AAT21] under a more general setting where the bug removal probability $p_j(t)$ is allowed to vary over time. However, in this model, we work with a fixed net debugging effect $(p_j - q_j)$, which does not depend on time. To apply the asymptotic results in Agustin, Agustin and Thompson [AAT21], we treat the fixed quantity $(p_j - q_j)$ as a special case of the time-varying function $p_j(t)$ by simply setting $p_j(t) = p_j - q_j$

for all $t \in [0, \tau]$. Since a constant function is a valid special case of a time-varying function, this substitution is justified and the asymptotic properties in (2.14) and (2.15) carry over directly to the current model without any additional modifications.

The above properties will be used in the simulation study and data analysis presented in the following sections of this thesis, specifically when determining the appropriate component size s that ensures the estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ performs well and produces stable and reliable results.

CHAPTER 3

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Selection of Component Size s

A Monte Carlo simulation study was conducted in order to investigate the behavior of the system reliability estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ as the component size s increases. The primary objective of this study was to identify the smallest value of s for which the sampling distribution of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ can be considered reasonably well approximated by a normal distribution. For each value of s under consideration, a total of 10,000 Monte Carlo replications were carried out to ensure sufficient numerical stability in the results.

To perform this investigation, a series system consisting of $m = 3$ components was considered. The parameter values used throughout the simulation were selected arbitrarily for illustrative purposes and are as follows: $\beta_0 = 12$, $\gamma_0 = (0.05, 0.07, 0.06)$, $\alpha_0 = (10, 12, 15)$, a stopping time of $\tau = 5$, debugging probabilities $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, p_3) = (0.9, 0.8, 0.85)$, and $\mathbf{q} = (q_1, q_2, q_3) = (0.2, 0.15, 0.3)$. The component size s was then varied systematically over the range $s = 1, 2, \dots, 30$, allowing for a comprehensive examination of its effect on the distributional properties of the estimator.

The true system reliability corresponding to the configuration described above is $\rho_{\text{true}} = 0.8663064$. A summary of the simulation results, including the empirical mean, standard deviation, and skewness of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ for selected values of $s = 1, \dots, 30$, is presented in Table 3.1.

The results reveal a clear and consistent pattern as s increases. For smaller values of s , the estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ displays relatively high variability and noticeable skewness, which suggests that the sampling distribution is asymmetric and has not yet reached a stable form. This behavior indicates that smaller component sizes may not be suitable for inference based on the normality assumption. However, as s increases gradually, two important trends

become apparent. First, the empirical mean of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ remains consistently close to the true value ρ_{true} throughout, which reflects the approximately unbiased nature of the estimator across all considered values of s . Second, the standard deviation decreases in a steady manner, demonstrating that the estimator becomes increasingly more precise and stable as the component size grows larger. Together, these observations suggest that a moderate value of s is sufficient to achieve a satisfactory approximation to normality, which will be discussed further in the following section.

Table 3.1: Monte Carlo results for system reliability estimates with varying component sizes s . The true system reliability is $\rho_{\text{true}} = 0.8663064$.

s	mean $\hat{\rho}_\tau$	sd($\hat{\rho}_\tau$)	skewness
1	0.8608567	0.0393887	0.3025870
2	0.8659475	0.0284659	0.4383945
3	0.8663550	0.0235212	0.3309125
5	0.8658217	0.0183290	0.2428758
10	0.8665317	0.0129851	0.1796094
15	0.8662388	0.0105547	0.1149991
20	0.8663482	0.0090954	0.0931149
25	0.8662386	0.0082640	0.1451558
26	0.8663163	0.0079744	0.0657131

To check whether the sampling distribution is close to normal, skewness was used as a diagnostic measure, with a threshold value of 0.08 adopted as a practical criterion. The results show that skewness gradually decreases as s increases, which reflects the distribution moving toward a more symmetric shape. The full results table has been included in Appendix A.1.

Graphical diagnostics also support this observation. Figure 3.1 shows histograms of the centered estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau - \rho_{\text{true}}$ for selected values of s . For small values of s , the distribution is clearly skewed, but as s increases, it becomes more symmetric and more concentrated around zero. Moreover, for small values of s , the estimates appear to be quite unstable, showing high variability across replications. This can be seen in Figure 3.1, which shows the histogram for $s = 5$ as an example of this instability, where the distribution is skewed and the estimates are spread widely around zero. As s increases, however, the estimates become noticeably more stable and consistent, reflecting a reduction in this variability. In particular, at $s = 26$, the histogram shows a clear bell-shaped pattern that is consistent with normality. Based on these results, $s = 26$ is selected as the appropriate component size for the rest of the analysis, as it is the smallest value of s for which the sampling distribution of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ behaves approximately normally.

Figure 3.1: Histograms of $\hat{\rho}_\tau - \rho_{\text{true}}$ for selected component sizes.

Figure 3.1: (Continued) Histograms of $\hat{\rho}_\tau - \rho_{\text{true}}$ for selected component sizes.

Figure 3.2 presents the corresponding Q-Q plots. For smaller values of s , the plotted points deviate from the reference line, especially in the tails. This can be seen clearly in Figure 3.2, which shows the Q-Q plot for $s = 5$. In this plot, the points at both ends move away from the reference line quite noticeably, which suggests that the tails of the distribution are heavier, and therefore the normality assumption does not seem to hold for such small values of s . As s increases, the points start to align more closely with the reference line. At $s = 26$, the Q-Q plot shows near-linear behavior with only minor deviations, which provides strong

evidence that the sampling distribution of $\hat{\rho}$ is approximately normal at this component size.

Figure 3.2: Q–Q plots of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ for selected component sizes.

Based on both the numerical and graphical evidence, approximate normality is first

achieved at $s = 26$. At this value, the estimator shows negligible bias, relatively low variability, and skewness below the selected threshold. Although $s = 25$ gives similar mean and variance properties, its skewness is still slightly above the threshold. Increasing to $s = 27$ does not bring any meaningful improvement.

Therefore, $s = 26$ is selected as the appropriate component size, as it provides a good balance between statistical accuracy and computational efficiency. Increasing s beyond this value leads to only small gains while requiring more computational effort.

Overall, the simulation results show that a component size of $s = 26$ is sufficient for the sampling distribution of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ to be well approximated by a normal distribution. This finding is consistent with the asymptotic theory, which states that the distribution of the estimator converges to normality as the component size increases. These results provide strong empirical support for the asymptotic normality of the estimator under increasing component size.

3.2 Selection of the Stopping Time

The stopping time τ plays an important role in determining how much debugging is carried out and, as a result, what the final system reliability estimate looks like. In this study, τ is varied over the interval $[5, 100]$, starting from an initial value of $\tau = 5$ and increasing gradually to examine its effect on reliability growth. The goal is to identify a value of τ beyond which additional testing no longer leads to meaningful improvement in system reliability.

For each value of τ , the Monte Carlo estimate $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ was computed, and the relative change between successive estimates was tracked using

$$\frac{|\hat{\rho}_{new} - \hat{\rho}_{old}|}{\hat{\rho}_{old}}.$$

This quantity measures how much the reliability estimate shifts from one step to the next, and when it becomes sufficiently small, it indicates that increasing τ further no longer produces

any meaningful change in the estimate. To focus only on the effect of τ , the component size was fixed at $s = 26$, as determined in Section 3.1, which ensures that the estimator behaves approximately normally with minimal Monte Carlo variability. Table 3.2 presents a selected subset of the Monte Carlo results for chosen values of τ .

Table 3.2: Monte Carlo estimates of system reliability ρ_τ^0 , standard deviation, and relative changes for selected stopping times τ (component size $s = 26$).

τ	ρ_τ^0	SD(ρ_τ^0)	Relative Change
5.00	0.8663	0.0078	NA
10.82	0.8898	0.0050	0.00841
20.51	0.9208	0.0031	0.00551
30.20	0.9435	0.0023	0.00420
51.53	0.9735	0.0013	0.00187
70.92	0.9867	0.0008	0.00092
100.00	0.9953	0.0004	0.00035

The results reveal a clear pattern of diminishing returns as τ grows. For small values of τ , the system has limited opportunity to remove defects, which leads to relatively low reliability estimates. In this range, reliability grows quickly and the relative change is noticeably large, reflecting the fact that each additional unit of testing still has a substantial impact. As τ increases, however, the rate of improvement slows down and the relative change decreases steadily, suggesting that most of the detectable defects have already been addressed and further testing contributes less and less to the overall estimate. Applying a relative change threshold of $\epsilon = 0.001$ as a practical stopping criterion, the optimal stopping time is identified as $\tau^* \approx 70.92$, meaning that testing beyond this point yields negligible gains in reliability.

The full numerical results supporting this analysis are included in Appendix A.2.

Figure 3.3: Monte Carlo estimates of system reliability ρ_τ^0 versus stopping time τ for component size $s = 26$. The curve flattens around $\tau^* \approx 70.92$, indicating diminishing returns in reliability growth.

Figure 3.3 shows how system reliability grows as τ increases. The curve starts at around 0.8663 when $\tau = 5$ and rises steeply through the early range, reflecting the fact that early debugging sessions are the most productive, a large number of bugs are removed in a short amount of time, leading to rapid improvements in reliability. As τ moves past 30 and toward 50, the curve begins to bend and the rate of growth slows down noticeably. Beyond $\tau^* \approx 70.92$, the curve becomes almost flat, sitting just below 0.99, and further increases in τ produce only very small additional gains. This flattening behaviour is a strong visual indicator that the system has reached a point of diminishing returns, where the remaining bugs are becoming increasingly difficult to find and remove.

To complement Figure 3.3 and provide a more precise basis for selecting τ^* , Figure 3.4 plots the relative change between successive reliability estimates directly against τ .

Figure 3.4: Relative change in Monte Carlo reliability estimates ρ_τ^0 versus stopping time τ for component size $s = 26$. The red dashed line shows the threshold $\varepsilon = 0.001$ and the green vertical line marks the optimal stopping time $\tau^* \approx 70.92$.

The red dashed horizontal line marks the stopping threshold of $\varepsilon = 0.001$ and the green vertical line marks the point where the relative change first drops below this threshold. Figure 3.4 makes the stopping decision much more explicit. At small values of τ , the relative change is large, starting above 0.009 near $\tau = 5$, which confirms that early testing produces substantial improvements. The curve then drops steeply through the range $\tau = 5$ to $\tau = 25$, followed by a more gradual decline from $\tau = 25$ to $\tau = 70$. At $\tau^* \approx 70.92$, the blue curve crosses below the red dashed threshold line for the first time, as marked by the green vertical line. Beyond this point, the relative change remains well below 0.001 all the way to $\tau = 100$, confirming that no meaningful improvement in reliability is achieved by continuing to test beyond τ^* . The two figures together therefore tell a consistent and complete story, Figure 3.3 shows the overall reliability growth pattern and Figure 3.4 pinpoints exactly where that growth becomes negligible.

Overall, the sequential approach used in this study first determining the appropriate component size by ensuring approximate normality of the estimator in Section 3.1, and then

identifying the optimal stopping time by evaluating the convergence of reliability with respect to τ in this section makes the analysis more structured, reliable, and easier to interpret.

3.3 Influence of Bug Removal and Introduction Probabilities on System Reliability

The reliability of a software system under imperfect debugging depends heavily on two key probabilities: p_j , the probability of successfully removing a bug from component j , and q_j , the probability of accidentally introducing a new bug during the removal process. In this study, the system consists of three components with component-specific probabilities $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, p_2, p_3)$ and $\mathbf{q} = (q_1, q_2, q_3)$. To investigate how changes in these probabilities affect the system reliability estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$, a sensitivity analysis was conducted by systematically increasing and decreasing each probability vector by 5%, 10%, and 15% from its baseline value, while holding the other vector constant.

All simulation scenarios in this section were carried out using the two key values established from the earlier investigations in this chapter. Specifically, the component size was fixed at $s = 26$, which was identified in Section 3.1 as the minimum value for which the sampling distribution of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ can be reasonably approximated by a normal distribution, and the stopping time was set to $\tau^* = 70.92$, which was determined in Section 3.2 as the optimal value that balances estimation accuracy and computational efficiency. The use of these values ensures that the sensitivity analysis is conducted under conditions that are both statistically justified and practically meaningful. Each simulation scenario consisted of 10,000 Monte Carlo replications, providing precise and reliable estimates of the mean system reliability and its associated variability across all configurations considered.

3.3.1 Effects of Bug Removal Probability p_j

Tables 3.3 and 3.4 present Monte Carlo results for increasing and decreasing p_j , respectively, with vectors shown and $\mathbf{q} = (0.2, 0.15, 0.3)$ held constant.

Table 3.3: Monte Carlo results for increasing p_j .

Increase	\mathbf{p} vector	mean $\hat{\rho}$	sd($\hat{\rho}$)
0%	(0.9, 0.8, 0.85)	0.9867047	0.0007667
5%	(0.945, 0.84, 0.892)	0.9888529	0.0007002
10%	(0.99, 0.88, 0.935)	0.9906568	0.0006476
15%	(1, 0.92, 0.977)	0.9918969	0.0005999

As p_j increases, the mean system reliability rises consistently, which confirms that more effective bug removal directly improves overall system performance. The standard deviation decreases slightly as well, indicating that the estimator remains precise and stable across different levels of p_j .

Table 3.4: Monte Carlo results for decreasing p_j .

Decrease	\mathbf{p} vector	mean $\hat{\rho}$	sd($\hat{\rho}$)
0%	(0.9, 0.8, 0.85)	0.9867047	0.0007667
5%	(0.855, 0.76, 0.807)	0.9841234	0.0008251
10%	(0.81, 0.72, 0.765)	0.9810607	0.0009075
15%	(0.765, 0.68, 0.722)	0.9774531	0.0009878

Reducing p_j leads to a clear decline in system reliability, while the variability of the estimator remains largely unaffected, indicating that the stability of the Monte Carlo estimates is maintained regardless of the bug removal effectiveness.

Figure 3.5: Side-by-side panel plot showing the behavior of the mean system reliability estimator $\hat{\rho}$ as p_j is varied. The left panel shows the decreasing scenario, while the right panel shows the increasing scenario. The shaded grey bands represent ± 1 standard deviation around the mean, and the red dashed line indicates the baseline value at 0% change.

To further illustrate these findings, Figure 3.5 presents a side-by-side panel plot showing the behavior of the mean system reliability estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ as p_j is varied, with the decreasing scenario displayed on the left panel and the increasing scenario on the right. The shaded grey bands represent ± 1 standard deviation around the mean, and the red dashed line marks the baseline value at 0% change as a reference. As can be seen clearly from the right panel, the mean $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ rises steadily above the baseline as p_j increases, and the shaded band remains consistently narrow throughout, which reflects the stable and precise estimation reported in Table 3.3. In contrast, the left panel shows that as p_j decreases, the mean $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ falls noticeably below the baseline, and the band widens slightly as the percentage change grows larger, which is consistent with the increasing standard deviation values observed in Table 3.4. Overall, the figure provides a clear visual confirmation of the numerical results, showing that the bug removal probability p_j has a meaningful and directional effect on system reliability, and

that higher values of p_j lead to both improved reliability estimates and tighter estimation precision.

3.3.2 Effects of Bug Introduction Probability q_j

Tables 3.5 and 3.6 summarize results for varying q_j while holding $\mathbf{p} = (0.9, 0.8, 0.85)$ constant.

Table 3.5: Monte Carlo results for increasing q_j .

Increase	\mathbf{q} vector	mean $\hat{\rho}$	sd($\hat{\rho}$)
0%	(0.2, 0.15, 0.3)	0.9867047	0.0007667
5%	(0.21, 0.158, 0.315)	0.9860067	0.0007783
10%	(0.22, 0.165, 0.33)	0.9852684	0.0008050
15%	(0.23, 0.172, 0.345)	0.9845214	0.0008207

As q_j increases, mean system reliability decreases, reflecting the negative impact of introducing new bugs during the debugging process, while the standard deviation remains small throughout, demonstrating the robustness of the Monte Carlo estimates.

Table 3.6: Monte Carlo results for decreasing q_j .

Decrease	\mathbf{q} vector	mean $\hat{\rho}$	sd($\hat{\rho}$)
0%	(0.2, 0.15, 0.3)	0.9867047	0.0007667
5%	(0.19, 0.142, 0.285)	0.9873462	0.0007393
10%	(0.18, 0.135, 0.27)	0.9879579	0.0007258
15%	(0.17, 0.128, 0.255)	0.9885565	0.0007099

Decreasing q_j consistently improves system reliability, with the standard deviation remaining low across all scenarios, confirming the stability and precision of the Monte Carlo estimates.

Figure 3.6: Side-by-side panel plot for the q_j sensitivity analysis. The left panel shows the decreasing scenario, while the right panel shows the increasing scenario. The grey shaded bands represent ± 1 standard deviation, and the red dashed line indicates the baseline reference at 0% change.

Figure 3.6 presents the corresponding panel plot for the q_j sensitivity analysis. As expected, the behavior is reversed compared to the p_j case. The right panel shows that increasing q_j pulls the mean $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ steadily below the baseline, with the shaded band widening slightly as the percentage change grows, which is consistent with the values reported in Table 3.5. The left panel shows the opposite, where decreasing q_j lifts the mean $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ above the baseline in a smooth and consistent manner, while the band narrows slightly, reflecting the small reduction in standard deviation seen in Table 3.6. This confirms that q_j has a clear directional effect on system reliability, and that keeping the rate of bug introduction low during the debugging process is an important factor in achieving higher and more stable reliability estimates.

3.3.3 A Joint Sensitivity Analysis of Bug Removal and Introduction Probabilities

To go beyond the one-at-a-time analysis in Sections 3.3.1 and 3.3.2, a joint sensitivity analysis was carried out for each component separately. For component j , the values of p_j and q_j were varied simultaneously over a fine grid while the parameters of the other two components were held at their baseline values. The resulting reliability estimates evaluated directly from the asymptotic closed-form expression given in equation (2.14), which is

$$\rho_\tau^0 = \frac{\beta^0}{\beta^0 + \sum_{j=1}^m \gamma_j^0 \alpha_j^0 e^{-\gamma_j^0(p_j - q_j)\tau}}$$

are displayed as individual reliability surface heatmaps in Figures 3.7, 3.8, and 3.9 for components 1, 2, and 3 respectively. In each plot, the x -axis shows p_j ranging from 0.6 to 1.0, the y -axis shows q_j ranging from 0.0 to 0.5, and the color scale transitions from red, indicating low reliability, to green, indicating high reliability.

Table 3.7: The range of ρ_τ^0 values observed across the grid for each component.

Component	Min ρ_τ^0	Max ρ_τ^0	Spread
1	0.962	0.989	0.027
2	0.949	0.989	0.040
3	0.948	0.993	0.045

To allow direct visual comparison across the three panels, a common color scale ranging from 0.95 to 0.99 was applied to Figures 3.7, 3.8, and 3.9. All three heatmaps share the same broad pattern. The values of ρ_τ^0 are highest in the bottom-right region of each panel, where p_j is large and q_j is small, corresponding to effective bug removal and minimal introduction of new defects. Conversely, ρ_τ^0 is lowest in the top-left region, where p_j is small and q_j is large, representing poor debugging performance.

This is consistent with the theoretical expectation that a larger $p_j - q_j$ gap drives higher reliability, so any combination that widens this gap improves ρ_τ^0 . The transition from red to green follows a curved arc rather than a strictly linear path, suggesting the presence of a critical boundary in the (p_j, q_j) space where ρ_τ^0 changes rapidly. Operating near this boundary would make the system highly sensitive to small fluctuations in debugging quality.

Figure 3.7: Component 1 system reliability surface heatmap.

For component 1, the reliability surface shown in Figure 3.7 is the flattest among the three components. As shown in Table 3.7, the values of ρ_τ^0 across the grid range from 0.962 at the lowest to 0.989 at the highest, a spread of just 0.027, which is the narrowest among all three components. Under the shared color scale, it is immediately visible that the panel appears almost entirely deep green, confirming that no matter what combination of p_1 and q_1 is chosen within the grid, ρ_τ^0 stays high and Component 1 has the weakest influence on the system reliability.

The diamond marker at the baseline $(p_1, q_1) = (0.9, 0.2)$ sits well inside the deep green region, comfortably away from any transition zone. This means that even if p_1 or q_1 were to shift moderately from their baseline values, ρ_τ^0 would not drop in any meaningful way. Overall, component 1 is the least sensitive component and ρ_τ^0 is quite robust to changes in

the respective debugging probabilities.

Figure 3.8: Component 2 system reliability surface heatmap.

For component 2, the picture is noticeably different. As shown in Table 3.7, the values of ρ_τ^0 across the grid range from 0.949 at the lowest to 0.989 at the highest, a spread of 0.040, which is wider than what was seen for component 1. Under the shared color scale, this is visible in Figure 3.8 through a more noticeable transition from red to green compared to Component 1, where the color shift is more spread out across the grid.

The diamond marker at the baseline $(p_2, q_2) = (0.8, 0.15)$ sits within the green region, so ρ_τ^0 remains at a healthy level under the current configuration. The low bug introduction probability $q_2 = 0.15$ keeps the baseline comfortably low on the y -axis, well away from the red region. However, since $p_2 = 0.8$ is the lowest bug removal probability among the three components, the baseline sits on the lower end of the x -axis, meaning that any further decrease in p_2 would quickly move the operating point toward the lighter green and yellow transition area. This makes component 2 more sensitive than component 1 in terms of bug removal performance, and suggests that maintaining p_2 at its current level or above is important for keeping ρ_τ^0 stable. A drop in p_2 would have a more noticeable effect here than a similar drop would in component 1.

Figure 3.9: Component 3 system reliability surface heatmap.

For component 3, the reliability surface shown in Figure 3.9 tells the most concerning story of the three. As shown in Table 3.7, the values of ρ_τ^0 across the grid range from 0.948 at the lowest to 0.993 at the highest, a spread of 0.045, which is the widest among all three components. Under the shared color scale, the color gradient in Figure 3.9 is visibly more varied than in Figures 3.7 and 3.8, confirming that the choice of p_3 and q_3 has the strongest influence on ρ_τ^0 .

The baseline $(p_3, q_3) = (0.85, 0.30)$ is positioned noticeably higher on the y -axis compared to the previous two components, with $q_3 = 0.30$ already sitting at the middle of the y -axis range. This means there is much less room for q_3 to increase before the operating point moves into the lighter green and yellow transition area. At the same time, a moderate drop in p_3 would push the baseline leftward toward the same transition zone. Both directions of movement carry a real risk of a noticeable drop in ρ_τ^0 , making this baseline the most exposed of the three.

The upper left corner of Figure 3.9 also shows the most visible red region under the shared scale, reflecting the largest drop in ρ_τ^0 under worst case parameter combinations. Overall, component 3 is the most sensitive component in the system and its debugging parameters deserve the closest attention when it comes to maintaining a high and stable ρ_τ^0 .

A clear ranking emerges from the three panels. Component 3 has the greatest influence on ρ_τ^0 , followed by component 2, with component 1 being the least influential. To understand why this ordering appears, it helps to think about the quantity $p_j - q_j$ for each component. This difference captures how efficiently a component is being debugged, a larger gap means bugs are being removed much faster than they are being introduced.

Looking at the baseline values used in this study, component 1 has $p_1 - q_1 = 0.70$, component 2 has $p_2 - q_2 = 0.65$, and Component 3 has $p_3 - q_3 = 0.55$. Component 3 has the smallest gap under these particular parameter values, which explains why it sits closest to the transition zone and is the most sensitive to parameter changes in this case.

From a practical standpoint, the key insight is that the component with the smallest $p_j - q_j$ gap will always be the most sensitive, regardless of which component that turns out to be. In this study it happens to be component 3, but for a different system or a different set of baseline values, the ranking could change entirely. This suggests that identifying the component with the narrowest $p_j - q_j$ gap may be a useful starting point in reliability improvement efforts, as in this study it corresponds to the component where parameter changes had the largest impact on ρ_τ^0 .

The one-at-a-time results in Sections 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 establish the general direction and magnitude of each effect, while the joint reliability surfaces in Section 3.3.3 reveal that the three components differ meaningfully in how much they influence ρ_τ^0 . The key takeaway is that it is not high q_j or low p_j alone that determines sensitivity, but how small the difference $p_j - q_j$ is. In a software system with imperfect debugging, the components where this gap is narrowest deserve the most attention, as even small parameter shifts there can lead to the largest drops in ρ_τ^0 .

CHAPTER 4

CONCLUSION

This study developed and analyzed a system reliability model for a series system of three components under an imperfect debugging framework. Unlike earlier models that assumed bugs are always removed with certainty, this model introduced two component-specific probabilities, p_j and q_j , which represent the probability of successfully removing a bug and the probability of introducing a new one during the debugging process, respectively. This makes the model more realistic and better suited for describing real-world software debugging scenarios.

A Monte Carlo simulation study was carried out to evaluate the performance of the system reliability estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$. The simulation results showed that a component size of $s = 26$ is sufficient for the sampling distribution of $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ to be well approximated by a normal distribution, which is consistent with the asymptotic theory. Using a relative change threshold of $\epsilon = 0.001$ as the stopping criterion, the optimal stopping time was identified as $\tau^* \approx 70.92$, beyond which additional testing yields only negligible improvements in reliability. The sensitivity analysis showed that system reliability is highly sensitive to both p_j and q_j . Increasing p_j or decreasing q_j consistently leads to higher system reliability, while the opposite changes reduce it. The joint analysis further revealed that the component with the smallest $p_j - q_j$ gap tends to have the greatest influence on overall system reliability. These findings provide useful practical guidance for software developers and managers, highlighting the importance of effective debugging practices and minimizing the introduction of new defects during the correction process.

There are several directions that could be explored in future work. First, p_j and q_j were assumed to be fixed constants in this study, but in practice these probabilities may change

over time as developers gain more experience. Allowing them to be time-varying could make the model even more realistic. Second, applying the model to real software failure data would be a valuable next step to validate the model in practice and to assess how well it fits actual data from different application domains. Finally, a Bayesian approach to estimation could also be considered in future work, as it would allow prior knowledge about the debugging process to be incorporated into the analysis, which could be particularly useful when the available failure data is limited.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Simulation Results

Table A.1: Monte Carlo simulation results summarizing the mean, standard deviation, and skewness of the system reliability estimator $\hat{\rho}_\tau$ for varying component sizes s . The true system reliability is $\rho_{true} = 0.8663064$.

s	Mean $\hat{\rho}_\tau$	SD $\hat{\rho}_\tau$	Skewness
1	0.8608567	0.039388671	0.30258702
2	0.8659475	0.028465853	0.43839446
3	0.8663550	0.023521225	0.33091254
4	0.8660874	0.020741178	0.29871846
5	0.8658217	0.018328970	0.24287579
6	0.8659528	0.016596646	0.24632767
7	0.8662458	0.015378118	0.24846140
8	0.8662530	0.014709635	0.20166384
9	0.8663469	0.013560753	0.19104032
10	0.8665317	0.012985072	0.17960945
11	0.8662498	0.012571344	0.15143360
12	0.8663971	0.011975435	0.17772670
13	0.8665299	0.011337123	0.16508555
14	0.8662903	0.011111063	0.16316000
15	0.8662388	0.010554661	0.11499915
16	0.8663292	0.010212573	0.15299661
17	0.8663179	0.009911781	0.17108770
18	0.8664162	0.009704376	0.14060276
19	0.8663936	0.009349468	0.08877680
20	0.8663482	0.009095363	0.09311493
21	0.8662600	0.008934023	0.10038642
22	0.8663950	0.008761682	0.13990864
23	0.8663771	0.008495932	0.09447754
24	0.8664160	0.008373112	0.09453691
25	0.8662386	0.008264045	0.14515582
26	0.8663163	0.007974436	0.06571315

Table A.2: Monte Carlo estimates of system reliability ρ_τ^0 and relative changes for stopping times τ with fixed component size $s = 26$.

τ	ρ_τ^0	SD	Relative Change
5.00	0.866306	0.007831	NA
6.94	0.874598	0.006642	0.009286
8.88	0.882433	0.005820	0.008957
10.82	0.889828	0.005016	0.008407
12.76	0.896801	0.004656	0.007628
14.69	0.903370	0.004346	0.007038
16.63	0.909553	0.003734	0.007020
18.57	0.915369	0.003519	0.006685
20.51	0.920834	0.003063	0.005513
22.45	0.925968	0.003034	0.005451
24.39	0.930786	0.002860	0.005362
26.33	0.935305	0.002620	0.004907
28.27	0.939542	0.002393	0.004402
30.20	0.943512	0.002278	0.004200
32.14	0.947231	0.002160	0.003965
34.08	0.950712	0.002054	0.003634
36.02	0.953970	0.001933	0.003413
37.96	0.957018	0.001787	0.003257
39.90	0.959869	0.001684	0.002955
41.84	0.962534	0.001590	0.002733
43.78	0.965025	0.001555	0.002554
45.71	0.967352	0.001436	0.002278
47.65	0.969527	0.001353	0.002364
49.59	0.971558	0.001299	0.002163
51.53	0.973455	0.001276	0.001868
53.47	0.975226	0.001194	0.001878
55.41	0.976880	0.001109	0.001684
57.35	0.978423	0.001097	0.001484
59.29	0.979864	0.001010	0.001532
61.22	0.981209	0.001029	0.001308
63.16	0.982463	0.000886	0.001331
65.10	0.983634	0.000902	0.001188
67.04	0.984727	0.000848	0.001160
68.98	0.985746	0.000786	0.001037
70.92	0.986697	0.000762	0.000916
72.86	0.987585	0.000721	0.000875

APPENDIX B

Simulation for component size s

```
library(moments)

set.seed(123)

B <- c(2, 12, 5)

m <- length(B)

tau <- 5

beta0 <- 12

gamma0 <- c(0.05, 0.07, 0.06)

alpha0 <- c(10, 12, 15)

p <- c(0.9, 0.8, 0.85)

q <- c(0.2, 0.15, 0.3)

n_sim <- 10000

S_values <- c(1:30)

X_true <- sapply(1:m, function(j) {
  alpha0[j]*(1 - exp(-gamma0[j]*(p[j]-q[j])*tau))/(p[j] - q[j])
})
```

```

rho_true <- beta0/(beta0 + sum(gamma0*alpha0*exp(-gamma0*(p - q)*tau)))

cat("True system reliability:", rho_true, "\n")

theta_true <- log(rho_true / (1 - rho_true))

one_simulation <- function(S) {

  N_0 <- rpois(1, S*beta0*tau)
  beta_hat <- N_0/(S*tau)

  gamma_hat <- numeric(m)
  alpha_hat <- numeric(m)

  for (j in 1:m) {
    Lambda_j <- S*gamma0[j]*(alpha0[j] - (p[j] - q[j])*X_true[j])*tau
    N_j <- rpois(1, Lambda_j)
    if (N_j == 0) return(NA)

    gamma_hat[j] <- N_j/(S*tau*(alpha0[j] - (p[j] - q[j])*X_true[j]))
    alpha_hat[j] <- N_j/(S*gamma_hat[j]*tau) + (p[j] - q[j])*X_true[j]
  }
}

```

```
denom <- beta_hat + sum(gamma_hat*(alpha_hat - (p - q)*X_true))  
if (denom <= 0) return(NA)  
  
rho_hat <- beta_hat/denom  
return(rho_hat)  
}
```

```
rho_storage <- vector("list", length(S_values))
```

```
results_S <- data.frame(  
  S = S_values,  
  rho_true = rho_true,  
  mean_rho_hat = NA,  
  sd_rho_hat = NA,  
  abs_bias = NA,  
  skew_rho_hat = NA)
```

```
for (i in seq_along(S_values)) {
```

```
  S_val <- S_values[i]
```

```
  rho_hat_vec <- replicate(n_sim, one_simulation(S_val))
```

```
  rho_hat_vec <- rho_hat_vec[!is.na(rho_hat_vec)]
```

```
results_S$mean_rho_hat[i] <- mean(rho_hat_vec)

results_S$sd_rho_hat[i] <- sd(rho_hat_vec)

results_S$abs_bias[i] <- abs(mean(rho_hat_vec) - rho_true)

theta_hat_vec <- log(rho_hat_vec / (1 - rho_hat_vec))

W_vec <- sqrt(S_val) * (theta_hat_vec - theta_true)

results_S$skew_rho_hat[i] <- skewness(W_vec)

rho_storage[[i]] <- rho_hat_vec
}

print(results_S)

threshold_skew <- 0.08

first_normal_index <- NA

for (i in seq_along(S_values)) {

  rho_hat_vec <- rho_storage[[i]]

  theta_hat_vec <- log(rho_hat_vec / (1 - rho_hat_vec))

  W_vec <- sqrt(S_values[i]) * (theta_hat_vec - theta_true)
```

```

if (is.na(first_normal_index) &&
abs(skewness(W_vec)) < threshold_skew) {
  first_normal_index <- i
  break
}
}

if (is.na(first_normal_index)) {
  cat("No S reaches approximate normality.\n")
} else {
  S_normal_threshold <- results_S$$[first_normal_index]
  cat("Approximate normality first achieved for S =",
      S_normal_threshold, "\n")

  i_before <- max(1, first_normal_index - 1)
  i_normal <- first_normal_index
  i_after <- min(length(S_values), first_normal_index + 1)

  plot_histogram <- function(index, title_suffix) {
    W_vec <- sqrt(S_values[index]) *
      (log(rho_storage[[index]] /

```

```

(1 - rho_storage[[index]])) - theta_true)

hist(W_vec, probability = TRUE, breaks = 25,
     col = "steelblue",
     border = "white",
     main = paste(title_suffix, "(S =", results_S$$S[index], ")"),
     xlab = expression(rho[true] - hat(rho)))
curve(dnorm(x, mean(W_vec), sd(W_vec)),
     col = "red3", lwd = 3, add = TRUE)
abline(v = mean(W_vec), col = "black", lwd = 2, lty = 2)
}

par(mfrow = c(1, 1), mar = c(4, 4, 3, 1))
plot_histogram(i_before, "Before Normality")
plot_histogram(i_normal, "Normality Achieved")
plot_histogram(i_after, "After Normality")

plot_qq <- function(index, title_suffix) {
  W_vec <- sqrt(S_values[index]) *
    (log(rho_storage[[index]] / (1 - rho_storage[[index]])) - theta_true)
  qqnorm(W_vec, main = paste(title_suffix,
    "(S =", results_S$$S[index], ")"))
}

```

```
    qqline(W_vec, col = "red", lwd = 2)
  }

  par(mfrow = c(1, 1), mar = c(4, 4, 3, 1))
  plot_qq(i_before, "QQ Before Normality")
  plot_qq(i_normal, "QQ Normality Achieved")
  plot_qq(i_after, "QQ After Normality")
}
```

APPENDIX C

Simulation for stopping time τ

```
library(moments)

set.seed(123)

B <- c(2, 12, 5)

m <- length(B)

S_fixed <- 26

tau_values <- seq(5, 100, length.out = 50)

beta0 <- 12

gamma0 <- c(0.05, 0.07, 0.06)

alpha0 <- c(10, 12, 15)

p <- c(0.9, 0.8, 0.85)

q <- c(0.2, 0.15, 0.3)

n_sim <- 1000

epsilon <- 0.001

compute_X_true <- function(tau) {
  sapply(1:m, function(j) {
```

```

    alpha0[j] * (1 - exp(-gamma0[j]*(p[j] - q[j])*tau))/(p[j] - q[j])
  })
}

one_simulation <- function(S, tau, X_true) {
  N_0 <- rpois(1, S*beta0*tau)
  beta_hat <- N_0/(S*tau)

  gamma_hat <- numeric(m)
  alpha_hat <- numeric(m)

  for (j in 1:m) {
    Lambda_j <- S*gamma0[j]*(alpha0[j] - (p[j] - q[j])*X_true[j])*tau
    N_j <- rpois(1, Lambda_j)
    if (N_j == 0) return(NA)

    gamma_hat[j] <- N_j/(S*tau*(alpha0[j] - (p[j] - q[j])*X_true[j]))
    alpha_hat[j] <- N_j/(S*gamma_hat[j]*tau) + (p[j] - q[j])*X_true[j]
  }

  denom <- beta_hat + sum(gamma_hat*(alpha_hat - (p - q)*X_true))
  if (denom <= 0) return(NA)
}

```

```
rho_hat <- beta_hat / denom

return(rho_hat)

}

results_tau <- data.frame(

  tau = tau_values,

  rho_true = NA,

  mean_rho_hat = NA,

  rel_change = NA)

rho_prev <- NA

optimal_tau <- NA

for (i in seq_along(tau_values)) {

  tau <- tau_values[i]

  X_true <- compute_X_true(tau)

  rho_hat_vec <- replicate(n_sim, one_simulation(S_fixed, tau, X_true))

  rho_hat_vec <- rho_hat_vec[!is.na(rho_hat_vec)]

  rho_mean <- mean(rho_hat_vec)
```

```
rho_sd <- sd(rho_hat_vec)

if (!is.na(rho_prev)) {
  rel_change <- abs(rho_prev - rho_mean) / rho_mean
} else {
  rel_change <- NA
}

results_tau$rho_true[i] <- beta0/
(beta0 + sum(gamma0*alpha0*exp(-gamma0*(p - q)*tau)))
results_tau$mean_rho_hat[i] <- rho_mean
results_tau$rel_change[i] <- rel_change

if (!is.na(rel_change) && rel_change < epsilon && is.na(optimal_tau)) {
  optimal_tau <- tau
}

rho_prev <- rho_mean
}

print(results_tau)

cat("Optimal stopping time based on relative change <", epsilon,
```

```
"is:", optimal_tau, "\n")

stop_index <- which(results_tau$rel_change < 0.001)[1]
tau_stop <- results_tau$tau[stop_index]

library(ggplot2)

ggplot(results_tau, aes(x = tau)) +
  geom_line(aes(y = rho_true, color = "True reliability"), size = 1) +
  geom_line(aes(y = mean_rho_hat, color = "Estimated reliability"),
  linetype = "dotted", size = 1) +
  geom_vline(aes(xintercept = tau_stop, color = "Stopping time"),
  size = 0.8) + scale_color_manual(
  values = c("True reliability" = "yellow",
  "Estimated reliability" = "darkred", "Stopping time" = "darkblue")
  ) +
  labs(
    x = expression(tau),
    y = expression(hat(rho)),
    title = "System Reliability vs Stopping Time",
    color = NULL
  ) +
```

```
theme_minimal(base_size = 12)
```

APPENDIX D

Sensitivity Analysis

D.1 Increase p_j

```
library(moments)

set.seed(123)

B <- c(2, 12, 5)

m <- length(B)

tau <- 70.92

beta0 <- 12

gamma0 <- c(0.05, 0.07, 0.06)

alpha0 <- c(10, 12, 15)

p_orig <- c(0.9, 0.8, 0.85)

q <- c(0.2, 0.15, 0.3)

n_sim <- 10000

S_val <- 26

X_true <- function(p) {
  sapply(1:m, function(j) {
```

```

    alpha0[j] * (1 - exp(-gamma0[j] * (p[j] - q[j]) * tau)) /
    (p[j] - q[j])
  })
}

rho_true <- function(p) {
  beta0 / (beta0 + sum(gamma0 * alpha0 * exp(-gamma0 * (p - q) * tau)))
}

cat("Base true system reliability:", rho_true(p_orig), "\n")

one_simulation <- function(S, p) {

  X_t <- X_true(p)

  N_0 <- rpois(1, S * beta0 * tau)

  beta_hat <- N_0 / (S * tau)

  gamma_hat <- numeric(m)
  alpha_hat <- numeric(m)

  for (j in 1:m) {
    Lambda_j <- S * gamma0[j] * (alpha0[j] - (p[j] - q[j]))

```

```

* X_t[j]) * tau

N_j <- rpois(1, Lambda_j)

if (N_j == 0) return(NA)

gamma_hat[j] <- N_j / (S * tau * (alpha0[j] - (p[j] - q[j])
* X_t[j]))

alpha_hat[j] <- N_j / (S * gamma_hat[j] * tau) + (p[j] - q[j])
* X_t[j]
}

denom <- beta_hat + sum(gamma_hat * (alpha_hat - (p - q) * X_t))

if (denom <= 0) return(NA)

rho_hat <- beta_hat / denom

return(rho_hat)
}

increase_vec <- c(0, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15)

increase_labels <- paste0(c(0, 5, 10, 15), "%")

results <- data.frame(

  Increase = increase_labels,

```

```
p_values = NA,  
rho_true = NA,  
mean_rho_hat = NA,  
sd_rho_hat = NA)  
  
for (i in seq_along(increase_vec)) {  
  p_new <- p_orig * (1 + increase_vec[i])  
  p_new <- pmin(p_new, 1)  
  
  results$p_values[i] <- paste(round(p_new, 3), collapse = ", ")  
  results$rho_true[i] <- rho_true(p_new)  
  
  rho_hat_vec <- replicate(n_sim, one_simulation(S_val, p_new))  
  rho_hat_vec <- rho_hat_vec[!is.na(rho_hat_vec)]  
  
  results$mean_rho_hat[i] <- mean(rho_hat_vec)  
  results$sd_rho_hat[i] <- sd(rho_hat_vec)  
}  
  
print(results)
```

D.2 Decrease q_j

```
library(moments)

set.seed(123)

B <- c(2, 12, 5)

m <- length(B)

tau <- 70.92

beta0 <- 12

gamma0 <- c(0.05, 0.07, 0.06)

alpha0 <- c(10, 12, 15)

p <- c(0.9, 0.8, 0.85)

q_orig <- c(0.2, 0.15, 0.3)

n_sim <- 10000

S_val <- 26

X_true <- function(p, q) {
  sapply(1:m, function(j) {
    alpha0[j] * (1 - exp(-gamma0[j] * (p[j] - q[j]) * tau)) /
    (p[j] - q[j])
  })
}
```

```
}

rho_true <- function(p, q) {
  beta0 / (beta0 + sum(gamma0 * alpha0 * exp(-gamma0 * (p - q) * tau)))
}

cat("Base true system reliability:", rho_true(p, q_orig), "\n")

one_simulation <- function(S, p, q) {

  X_t <- X_true(p, q)

  N_0 <- rpois(1, S * beta0 * tau)

  beta_hat <- N_0 / (S * tau)

  gamma_hat <- numeric(m)
  alpha_hat <- numeric(m)

  for (j in 1:m) {
    Lambda_j <- S * gamma0[j] * (alpha0[j] - (p[j] - q[j]) *
      X_t[j]) * tau
    N_j <- rpois(1, Lambda_j)
    if (N_j == 0) return(NA)
  }
}
```

```

gamma_hat[j] <- N_j / (S * tau * (alpha0[j] - (p[j] - q[j]) *
X_t[j]))
alpha_hat[j] <- N_j / (S * gamma_hat[j] * tau) + (p[j] - q[j]) *
X_t[j]
}

denom <- beta_hat + sum(gamma_hat * (alpha_hat - (p - q) * X_t))
if (denom <= 0) return(NA)

rho_hat <- beta_hat / denom
return(rho_hat)
}

decrease_vec <- c(0, 0.05, 0.10, 0.15)
decrease_labels <- paste0(c(0, 5, 10, 15), "%")

results <- data.frame(
  Decrease = decrease_labels,
  q_values = NA,
  rho_true = NA,
  mean_rho_hat = NA,

```

```
sd_rho_hat = NA)

for (i in seq_along(decrease_vec)) {
  q_new <- q_orig * (1 - decrease_vec[i])
  q_new <- pmax(q_new, 0)

  results$q_values[i] <- paste(round(q_new, 3), collapse = ", ")
  results$rho_true[i] <- rho_true(p, q_new)

  rho_hat_vec <- replicate(n_sim, one_simulation(S_val, p, q_new))
  rho_hat_vec <- rho_hat_vec[!is.na(rho_hat_vec)]

  results$mean_rho_hat[i] <- mean(rho_hat_vec)
  results$sd_rho_hat[i] <- sd(rho_hat_vec)
}

print(results)
```